

Phenols as Corrosion Inhibitors for Aluminium Alloy (3003) in Hydrochloric acid solution

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ELDRIDGE¹ reviewed the corrosion of aluminium and its prevention in hydrochloric acid. It has been pointed out that phenols can inhibit the corrosion of aluminium in hydrochloric acid², although phenols as such are corrosive to aluminium at high temperature³. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study different types of phenols such as phenol, resorcinol, pyrogallol, β -naphthol and α -naphthol as corrosion inhibitors for 3003 aluminium in hydrochloric acid solution.

Experimental

The aluminium sheet (S.W.G. 22) used had the following composition: Al = 98, Cu = 0.15, Mn = 1.0, Fe = 0.75 and Si = 0.6% maximum. Rectangular specimens of size 3 × 6 cm were used. Preparation, testing and cleaning procedures adopted have been described in earlier publication⁴. The results obtained by weight loss method are given in Table 1. The results of polarization studies are represented in Figs. 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—CORROSION OF 3003 ALUMINIUM IN 0.5N HYDROCHLORIC ACID AND ITS INHIBITION BY PHENOLS

Inhibitor ($2.4 \times 10^{-3}M$ concentration)	1 day		Temp : $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ 2 Days	
	Loss mg	Inhibition	Loss mg	Inhibition
Phenol	1125	—	1230	—
Resorcinol	237	79	307	75
Pyrogallol	198	82	225	82
β -naphthol	142	88	200	84
α -naphthol	310	72	843	31
	202	82	153	87

Fig. 1. Effect of current densities on the cathode and anode potential of 3003 aluminium.
AA'—uninhibited 0.5N HCl; BB'—Phenol;
CC'—Resorcinol; DD'—Pyrogallol.

Fig. 2. Effect of current densities on the cathode and anode potential of 3003 aluminium.

AA'— α -naphthol

BB'— β -naphthol.

Discussion

The efficiency of these compounds in inhibiting corrosion of 3003 aluminium alloy in 0.5N hydrochloric acid is as follows: α -naphthol \approx Pyrogallol > Resorcinol > β -naphthol > Phenol.

Reactivity in electrophilic aromatic substitution depends, then, upon the tendency of a substituent group to release or withdraw electrons. A group like -OH releases electrons activates the ring. This is not due to their inductive effect but due to resonance. An activating group activates all positions of the benzene ring, even the positions meta to it are more reactive than any single position in the benzene ring itself. The activating group directs ortho and para simply because it activates ortho and para positions much more than it does the meta. The effect of -OH group on electrophilic aromatic substitution can be accounted for by assuming that oxygen can share more than a pair of electrons with the ring and can accommodate a positive charge. Due to activation of benzene ring pyrogallol is more effective than phenol and β -naphthol.

Cathode becomes highly polarized when external e.m.f. is applied. Sudden increase in cathodic polarization at low current densities indicates the formation of a film over the cathodic parts of the specimens. The shift of the steady state potential in the more negative side indicates film formation on the metal surface.

Thus in the above study general adsorption theory is applicable for the mechanism of inhibition.

References

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